

Rome, 23 February 2026

The table attached to this document specifies the features of the Shiga Toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC) and other diarrhoeagenic *E. coli* (DEC) reference strains available at the EURL-PH-FWDB for the Network Laboratories.

The strains are provided as pure cultures in soft agar, prepared as fresh passages of the reference strains, checked for the specified features during preparation. The stab-agar cultures can be stored at room temperature and are stable for up to six weeks since the date of preparation, reported in each certificate provided together with the reference materials. The strains must be cultured before that date to prepare passages that will be stored frozen after the addition of crio-preservedatives.

To prepare passages of the strains, use a sterile 1 µl loop to pick part of the culture from the vial and inoculate it in nutrient broth (e.g. TSB). Streak the enrichment culture onto solid agar plates.

A certificate will be provided together with the reference materials.

Please note that the reference strains are provided for being used as positive controls in methods set up, for quality assurance purposes, and specific assays (e.g. determination of the serogroup, presence of virulence genes). Any other use or their distribution to other laboratories is not allowed without formal consent from the EURL-PH-FWDB.

BIOSAFETY WARNING

Diarrhoeagenic *E. coli* are human pathogens, and particularly Shiga-toxin-producing *E. coli* can cause severe disease such as the haemolytic uremic syndrome. Laboratory acquired infections have been reported. Therefore, they should be handled according to the national biosafety procedures for pathogenic strains and particular attention must be paid when manipulating STEC pure cultures.

Annex 1. List of STEC and other DEC reference strains available at the EURL-PH-FWDB

Strain	Genotype	Serogroup	Features
EURL-VTEC A07	<i>eae</i>	O111	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O111 serogroup
EURL-VTEC B07	<i>eae; stx2::IS3</i>	O103	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O103 serogroup
EURL-VTEC C07	<i>eae; stx1; stx2</i>	O157	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O157 serogroup
EURL-VTEC D07	<i>eae; stx1; stx2</i>	O26	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O26 serogroup
EURL-VTEC E07	<i>eae; stx1</i>	O145	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O145 serogroup
C679-12	<i>aggR; aaiC</i>	O104	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O104:H4 serotype and for <i>aggR</i> and <i>aaiC</i> genes
H307B	<i>aggR; aaiC</i>	O91	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O91 serogroup
6182-50	-	O113	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O113 serogroup
39w	-	O121	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O121 serogroup
Cigleris	<i>eae</i>	O128ab	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O128 serogroup
Su3912-41	-	O55	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O55 serogroup
CDC2950-54	-	O146	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O146 serogroup
EF 129	<i>eae</i>	O45	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O45 serogroup
ED1374	<i>eae; stx2</i>	O80	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for O80 serogroup
ED747	<i>stx1a; stx2a</i>	O48	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx1a</i> and <i>stx2a</i> subtypes
ED755	<i>stx1c; stx2b</i>	O174	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx1c</i> and <i>stx2b</i> subtypes
ED753	<i>stx1d</i>	O8	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx1d</i> subtype
ED748	<i>stx2b; stx2c</i>	O174	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2b</i> and <i>stx2c</i> subtypes
ED751	<i>stx2d</i>	O73	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2d</i> subtype
ED756	<i>stx2e</i>	O139	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2e</i> subtype
ED754	<i>eae; stx2f</i>	O128	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2f</i> subtype

ED752	<i>stx2g</i>	O2	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2g</i> subtype
SSI-NN14	<i>lt; stp</i>	O78	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>lt</i> and for <i>stp</i> (porcine)
EA22	<i>sth</i>	Ond	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>sth</i> (human)
SSI-OO15	<i>ipaH</i>	O124	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>ipaH</i>
STEC299	<i>stx2h</i>	O102	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2h</i>
CB10366	<i>stx2i</i>	O9	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2i</i>
OLC-1685	<i>stx2j</i>	O158	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2j</i>
12GZSW01	<i>stx2k</i>	O159	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2k</i>
1610T27873	<i>stx2l</i>	O65	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2l</i>
2001F31428	<i>stx2m</i>	O96	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2m</i>
2017C-4317	<i>stx2n</i>	O23	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2n</i>
03-3638	<i>stx2o</i>	O85	<i>E. coli</i> control strain for <i>stx2o</i>